

A Study on Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act and Social Capital: An Economic Analysis in Kovilpetti Block at Thoothukudi District

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Sheeba, E., and M. Subha. "A Study on Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act and Social Capital: An Economic Analysis in Kovilpetti Block at Thoothukudi District." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2019, pp. 139–46.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595750>

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Abstract

MGNREGA is the flagship welfare program me of the government, thus public work offering relatively predict table employment opportunities are particularly effective in showing rural development. A number of centrally sponsored schemes have been implemented under rural development Mission and welfare of the poor. But MGNREGA is one of the greatest experiments undertaken in India to eradicate rural poverty. The scheme has been launched to supplement the error and gaps of all previous schemes with the involvement of Panchayats, civil society and local administration. Poor families weretargeted to get benefits of employment and livelihood to supplement their family income. And improve the quality life of rural area and purchase power in rural people. The main objective of the study is to evaluate and understand the social capital and economic analysis of MGNREGS in the Kovilpetti block.

Introduction

The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) enacted on 7th September, 2005 is a landmark legislation which empowers the rural population with the legal right to demand work. One can see the NREGA as a shift from supply side to a demand side approach. The Act aims at enhancing livelihood security of households in rural areas of the Country by providing at least 100days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every household which has adult members who volunteer to do unskilled manual work. On February 2, 2006 with great hope and hype, the NREGA came into force, in its first phase, covering 200 districts across the Country. The second phase beginning 2007 – 08, covered an additional 130 districts totaling to 330. The other 266 districts have been notified on 28th September, 2007 where the NREGA came into force w.e.f. 1st April, 2008. Thus fulfilling the commitment of the Government is to implement the programme in all the districts of the country. This is the largest ever public employment programme visualized

in human history. The National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (NREGS) was renamed as Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Scheme (MGNREGS) on October 2, 2009. At the national level, employment was provided to 4.1 crore households in 2010-11 upto December, 2010. Women constitute 50 per cent of the total beneficiaries while Scheduled Castes accounted for 23 per cent and Scheduled Tribes 17 per cent under MGNREGS in 2010-11. Wage rates were enhanced by 17-30 per cent by linkage with Consumer Price Index for agricultural labour calculated on the basis of Rs. 100 or the actual wage rate, whichever is higher as on April 1, 2009. Around 9.38 crore accounts were opened in post offices/banks leading to their financial inclusion of water conservation, irrigation and land development accounted for over 75 per cent of works taken up in 2017-18. Over 76 lakh works taken up under MGNREGS so far.

Review of Literature

Mesh Deka et al. (2015) in the paper titled “Employment Generation and social capital formation: A Study of the impact of MGNREGA in Assam” emphasizes on the impact of MGNREGA on the development of employment and social capital formation. It has been observed that there exists a positive impact on the two variables and it has also been seen that it is a game changer in the field of economic and rural development of the country.

Das and Darshana (2016) in the paper titled “Role of MGNREGA in Rural Employment: A Study of Barpeta District of Assam, India” states that India is an agrarian country and most of the population of the country belongs to rural population. The policy makers have implemented various schemes such as IRDP, NREP, RLEGP etc but still the rural population was facing with the unemployment and acute poverty. To remove this problem govt. came up with the MGNREGA initiative. The study emphasizes on the object and implications of MGNREGA Act in rural areas and on the natural resources. It also focuses on the women participation in the scheme and role of MGNREGA in the sustainable rural development. It has been suggested that government should adopt more steps for its proper implementation.

Saikia et al. (2017) in the paper titled “Impact of MGNREGA on Rural Livelihood in Assam with special reference to Kamrup District of Assam.” highlights the implementation process of MGNREGA and its impact on the rural livelihood. It states that MGNREGA is the game changing step in the area of rural development but in Assam it is gaining momentum in a slower way. The paper also focuses the faulty implementation strategy has ruined the spirit of the programme. Religion and street biasness and favoritism in the case of distribution of job card, dominance of leading families, defective leadership and improper coordination among the stakeholders has become hurdles in the programme.

Vigneswar V, Kirubakaran K (2018) in our results most of the responses are belong to the age group of 45-60, because after reached this age group their opportunities in employment were reduced and they don't have physical strength and lack in efficiency to do tough works, MGNREGA specifically targeted this age group for to improve their economic status and MGNREGA indirectly empowers the women community in giving employment opportunities to them because they started to earn and their dependency level with the men gradually reduced and this is reflected in our results that's the 48.5% of the responses are belongs to the women community and there is no proper awareness created by the officials through MGNREGA scheme and it is resulted into lack of knowledge about these scheme/ act among the rural people and their job cards were not prepared under gram panchayat because in most of the villages MGNREGA schemes are not directly undertaken by gram panchayat.

Objectives

- To study the concept and structure of the Act.
- To study the socio capital in MGNREGS members in koilpetti block.
- To study the Economic analysis of MGNREGS on their areas.
- To provide effective findings & suggestions for the improveof the scheme and members.

Methodology

The methodology adopted for the study is based on Primary and secondary data. The primary data participants were selected through convenience sampling from the area of kovilpetti block. The data were 30 samples in a random manner. The data has been collected from differentsecondary sources such as books, websites, journals, etc.

Socio Economic Analysis of Workers

The demographic characteristics in nuclear family system are more prevent among the poor due to low income and inability to share their benefits with other members especially during lean seasons. In this section an attempt is made to discuss the demographic characteristics such as gender, age, marital status, religion, community, literacy level and the like.

Table – I Gender Wise Classification

S.No	Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Male	08	27
2	Female	22	73
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

It reveals that majority 73 percent of the respondents are female while 27 percent of the male respondents are joining the MGNREGS.

Table – II Age Wise Classification

S.No	Age [In years]	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Below 25 years	02	07
2	25-35 years	11	37
3	35-50 years	09	30
4	Above 50 years	08	26
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shown that 37 percent of the respondents are between 25-35years, 30 percent of the respondents are between 35-50 years, 26 percentage of the respondent are above 50 age group, and only 7 percent of the respondents are below 25 age of the MGNREGS.

Table- III Religion Wise Classification

S.No	Religion	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Hindu	20	67
2	Christians	08	27

3	Muslim	02	06
4	Others	00	00
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

The above tables shown that 67 percent of the respondents are Hindu, 27 percent of the respondents are Christian, and only 6 percentage of the respondent are Muslim in the MGNREGS.

Table IV Religion Wise Classification

S.No	Religion	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	OC	02	07
2	BC	11	37
3	MBC	07	23
4	SC/ST	10	33
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shown that 37 percent of MGNREGS members are BC religion, 33 percentage of the respondent are SC/ST, 23 percentage of the respondent are MBC, only 7 percentage of the respondent are OC religion.

Table V Educational level

S.No	Educational level	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Illiterate	10	33
2	Primary	15	50
3	Secondary	04	13
4	Degree	01	04
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shown that 50 percent of MGNREGS members are primary education, 33 percentage of the respondent are Illiterate, 13 percentage of the respondent are secondary education level, only 4 percentage of the respondent are degree holders.

Tables VI Marital Status

S.No	Marital status	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Un married	01	04
2	Married	24	80
3	Widowed	03	10
4	Divorced	02	06
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shown that 80 percent of MGNREGS members are married, 10 percentage of the respondent are widowed, 6 percentage of the respondent are divorced, only 4 percentage of the respondent are unmarried.

Tables VII Type of Family

S.No	Type of family	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Nuclear	26	87
2	Joint family	04	13
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shown that 87 percent of the respondents are nuclear family in the MGNREGS and, only 13 percentage of the respondent are joint family.

Tables VIII Status of House

S.No	Status of house	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Own	27	90
2	Rent	03	10
Total		30	100

Source: primary data

The above table shown that 87 percent of the respondents are own house in the MGNREGS and, only 10 percentage of the respondent are house rent.

Table IX Size of the Family

S.No	Size of the family	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Below 2 members	09	30
2	3-6	15	50
3	7-9	02	07
4	Above 9	04	13
Total		30	100

Source: primary data

The above table shown that 50 percent of the respondents are below 2 member , 30 percent of the respondents are between 3-6 members ,13 percentage of the respondent are above 9 members, and only 7 percent of the respondents are between 7-9 family member of the MGNREGS.

Table –X Working Years

S.No	Working years	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Below 3	02	07
2	3-6	11	37
3	6-9	05	17
4	Above 9	12	40
Total		30	100

Source: primary data

The above table shown that 40 percent of the respondents are above 9 years working the MGNREGS , 37 percent of the respondents are between 3-6 years ,17 percentage of the respondent are 6-9 years, and only 7 percent of the respondents are below 3 years.

Table –XI House Hold Asset

S.No	House hold asset	No.of respondents	Percentage
1.	Below Rs.100000	03	10
2.	Between Rs.200000 -400000	15	50
3.	Between Rs.400000 -600000	10	33
4.	Above 600000	02	07
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shown that 50 percent of the respondents are between Rs.200000-400000 house hold assets in the MGNREGS, 33 percentage of the respondent are Rs.400000 -600000, 10 percentage of the respondents are below Rs. 100000 and only 07 percentage of the respondent are above Rs.600000 house hold assets.

Table --- XII Annual Income

S.No	Annual income	No.of respondents	Percentage
1.	Below Rs.100000	07	23
2.	Between Rs.100000 -200000	12	40
3.	Between Rs.200000 -400000	09	30
4.	Above 400000	02	07
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shown that 40 percent of the respondents are between Rs.100000-200000 annual income in the MGNREGS, 30 percentage of the respondent are Rs.200000 - 400000, 23 percentage of the respondents are below Rs.100000 and only 07 percentage of the respondent are above Rs.600000 of the annual income.

Table XIII Met their Money

S.No	Met their money	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Food expenditure	10	33
2	Pay interest	03	10
3	Savings	08	27
4	Purchase the durable goods	04	13
5	Expenditure on education	05	17
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shown that 33percent of the respondents are met their money for food expenses in the MGNREGS, 27 percentage of the respondent are savings, 13 percentage of the respondents are purchase of durable goods, 17 percentage are education expensesand only 10 percentage of the respondent are pay the interest.

Table XIV Satisfaction Level

S.No	Satisfaction Level	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	26	87
2	No	04	13
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

It reveals that majority 87 percent of the respondents are satisfied the MGNREGS while 13 percent of the respondents are not satisfied in this scheme.

Findings

- 73 percent of the respondents are female.
- 37 percent of the respondents are between 25-35 years.
- 67 percent of the respondents are Hindu.
- 37 percent of MGNREGS members are BC religion.
- 50 percent of MGNREGS members are primary education.
- 80 percent of MGNREGS members are married.
- 87 percent of the respondents are nuclear family.
- 87 percent of the respondents are own house in the MGNREGS.
- 50 percent of the respondents are below 2 members.
- 40 percent of the respondents are above 9 years working the MGNREGS.
- 50 percent of the respondents are between Rs.200000-400000 house hold assets in the MGNREGS.
- 40 percent of the respondents are between Rs.100000-200000 annual incomes in the MGNREGS.
- 33 percent of the respondents are met their money for food expenses in the MGNREGS.
- 87 percent of the respondents are satisfied the MGNREGS.

Conclusion

The study was carried out in Koilpettei, a block widely presented as a success in terms of MGNREGAS implementation, and describes who participates in the scheme and how success is understood and expressed at different social and bureaucratic levels. In terms of MGNREGA's outcomes, we conclude that the scheme is benefitting the poorest household women in particular – especially in terms of providing a safety net and as a tool for poverty alleviation. The research has highlighted the importance of social capital and economic analysis the MGNREGA has resulted in positive.

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